

Secondary minerals from old smelter slags from the Puerto de Mazarrón area, Mazarrón, Murcia, Spain.

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In the Mazarrón area there are a series of mineralizations of silver-bearing galena that were exploited long before Roman times. Remains of very old smelters are found close to the mines, in the Cabezo de San Cristóbal and in the Coto Fortuna, and also on the coast, in Isla Plana (La Gacha), Cabezo del Castellar and Punta de Nares and Cabezo del Gavilán (or de los Gavilanes), and in Loma del Alamillo. Proof of the importance of these smelters was found in a Phoenician wreck, dated to 650 BC, which sank near the coast of Puerto de Mazarrón, carrying a cargo of 2.8 tons of cakes of oxidized lead residues, produced in the process of obtaining silver by cupellation, and destined for the recovery of the remaining lead (Miñano, 2013). Roman era mining and smelting gave rise to huge slag heaps which, despite the slag from the silver-rich galena still being rich in lead, was abandoned because the procedure used had prioritized the extraction of silver and economizing the coal (Bellón, 2008),

leaving behind a significant proportion of oxidized lead materials from the cupellation process.

Some of the Roman slag heaps were recycled starting in 1584, but most of them remained untouched until the 1840s, when a real exploitative “fever” occurred, both in Mazarrón as well as in Cartagena and elsewhere. Around twenty Roman slag heaps were registered and exploited in Mazarrón, most of them in the Susaña area, located between the Rambla de las Moreras and the Mazarrón road to Puerto de Mazarrón, and on the Loma de Herrerías. Other slag exploitations were carried out in El Alamillo, El Hondón, and Playa de los Gavilanes (Guillén, 1999).

Old smelters on the coast

Nowadays few old smelters remain on the coast, due to changes in the coastline, and urbanization. Nor are there many remains of slags, since those that existed, from cupellation processes, were rich enough in lead to be

Map of the surroundings of Puerto de Mazarrón showing the slag heap of the Santa Elisa smelter (A) and some antique coastal slag dumps.

B. Cabezo del Castellar, Punta de Nares, and Cabezo del Gavilán

C. Punta del Rihuete and Playa Alamillo

D. La Gacha-Florida Complex

E. Casas del Caraleño

recycled for the most part during the 19th century. In some places you can still see slags, both ancient ones from Roman times, and relatively modern ones dating from the late nineteenth or early twentieth century. In all cases, the action of seawater has led to the formation of secondary minerals, similar to those of other classical or even relatively modern slag heaps, such as those of Laurion, Greece.

Cabezo del Gavilán is located just west of the Mazarrón marina, and further west of this point the Cabezo del Castellar is located (B on the map). Between these are situated La Pava beach and Nares beach, separated from each other by the Punta de Nares. Metallurgical activities in pre-Roman times have been documented in the Cabezo del Gavilán. The presence of slags, in small quantities, has also been observed at Punta de Nares (Ramallo, 2005).

In Punta del Rihuete, located at the mouth of the Rambla de los Lorentes, 1 km NE of the fishing port of Mazarrón, as well as in Playa Alamillo, located immediately north (C on the map), abundant slags were found. In the area located on the other side of the road, currently urbanized, remains of Roman buildings were found, including a water distribution pond and a high imperial town, now almost completely eliminated (Amante *et al.*, 1996).

On the beach you can currently see antique looking slags mixed with other apparently modern ones.

At the extreme east of Playa Negra, on both sides of the road, near the facilities of the Instituto Español de Oceanografía y el Mar, in an area known as La Gacha (gacha being a local term to designate slags) and La Florida (D on the map) are deposits of Roman slags, which in places form important concentrations, and which were partly recycled in the mid-19th century, given that at some spots they include, in addition to the galena processing slags, cupellation litharge cakes, very rich in lead. Some lead ingots were even found in the 19th century (Villasante, 1891), and in 1980 another was found with part of the smelter's proprietary brand inscription (Ramallo, 2005). The furnaces were located on the other side of the current highway. These slags were already cited by Domergue (1987) and are related to a metallurgical complex active from the 1st century B.C. till the first half of the 1st century A.C.

The archaeological remains have been disturbed by modern breaks and subdivisions (Ramallo and Arana, 1985), and currently form part of the catalogued and protected archaeological zone known as La Gacha-Florida Complex, which extends towards the east almost to the border with the municipality of Cartagena (Ministry of Culture and Tourism, 2014).

The Casas del Caraleño are located about 375 meters inland in the area where the Rambla de Villalba flows into the sea (E on the map). On the beach west and east of the Rambla there are accumulations of old slags,

which are probably related to the extensive remains of buildings located on an elevation near the coast around 250 meters east of the Rambla (Correa, 2004). Depending on the activity of the sea and accumulation of sand, sometimes the slags are better exposed on the east or west of the Rambla. Roman slags have also been found in areas already somewhat distant from the current coast, such as the Loma de Herrerías, north of El Alhamillo, where Roman slags have been found crossed by the road from Mazarrón to Puerto de Mazarrón. A Roman smelting furnace has also been found in this area (Ramallo and Arana, 1985). Another area where slags have been noticed is in the vicinity of the Casa del Collado Blanco.

Modern smelters

Smelting the argentiferous galena has been carried out from the pre-Roman era up to modern times by a system that remains essentially unchanged. Two main stages can be distinguished: first, the reduction of the metals to obtain lead with its silver still included (argentiferous lead, the so-called "unwrought lead") and second, the displacement, to separate silver and other elements from the lead (some of them harmful to its industrial use) that once purified receives the name "sweet lead". Initially, the method used was cupellation, in which silver was left as a free metal; lead was transformed partly into litharge, absorbed into the material of the cupel (the cup), and partly into slags. Metallic lead could then be recovered through a new reduction process. Subsequently, more modern procedures were introduced, such as Parkes' method, recovering silver with zinc, and Harris' method, which selectively oxidized arsenic and antimony.

In 1839, the Jaroso vein was discovered in the Sierra Almagrera, Almería, with which the exploitation of argentiferous galena regained in Spain an importance that it had not seen since Roman times. In November 1840, the export of argentiferous lead as such was prohibited, forcing the process of displacement to be carried out in Spain. Technological shortcomings caused the smelter installation process to be slow, and the results were quite poor. In August 1852, the export of silver-rich lead was liberalized, in part because of the high cost of the coal needed to carry out the displacement process and in part because silver production was larger than the needs of the mints. The consequence was the disappearance in Spain of most of the smelters that separated the two elements Pb and Ag, and so the specialization in the extraction of lead from ore, without refining it.

In May 1864, Juan Antonio Gómez Paredes, a local businessman, asked the Mazarrón city council for the concession of a plot of land at the Cabezo del Faro, in the Port of Mazarrón, for the construction of a mineral smelter (Zapata and Fernández, 2006).

This smelter, known by the name of La Esperanza, had six calcination furnaces and two melting furnaces, but it was only in operation for a short time (Villasante, 1891). Its fireplace was located in the upper part of the Cabezo del Faro.

The Santa Elisa smelter

The discovery in 1883 of the Prodigio vein, with a wealth of minerals that lived up to its name, resulted in the arrival of foreign investors who, like the Compagnie d'Aguilas, acquired concessions and modernized the extraction, drainage facilities and transportation, increasing production considerably.

The Compañía Metalúrgica de Mazarrón was founded on January 31, 1885, with the aim of processing minerals from this municipality, although it would also partially use minerals from the Sierra de Cartagena, or from even more remote areas such as Sierra Almagrera and Linares. It had its registered office in Madrid, with an initial capital stock of 750,000 pesetas represented by 1,500 shares of 500 pesetas each. Of these shares, 400 were subscribed by Banco General de Madrid, 300 by

Hugo Andreac, representing the company Deutsche Gold- und Silber-Scheideanstalt vormals Rössler AG (later Degussa), dedicated to the refining and trade of silver and gold and headquartered in Frankfurt, 260 by G. Henfrey & Co., an English company with lead mines and smelters in Italy, 100 by Ernesto Greif, domiciled in Mazarrón, who had run the Calvet displacement factory in Garrucha, 100 by Jacob SH Stern, 90 by Ph. N. Schmidt and 125 by the company Johan Goll and Sons, all the latter three domiciled in Frankfurt, and 125 by the company of the Neufville family (Anonymous, 1885a). The Neufville family were the owners of the La Cruz smelter, in Linares. In addition, 300 founder certificates were issued, which gave preferential right to the acquisition of new shares issued within a period of ten years after the creation of the company. In June 1887, it was agreed to increase the share capital from the original 750,000 pesetas to 2,500,000 pesetas, by issuing 3,500 new shares of 500 pesetas each (García Lastra, 1887). The Compañía Metalúrgica de Mazarrón, unlike almost all other mining companies with foreign capital, was a limited company founded under Spanish law, based in Spain, and with important Spanish personalities on the board of directors, with a purely nominal role. In 1885 the president of the council was Cristóbal Colón de la Cerda, Duke of Veragua. Joaquín de la Gándara, Marqués of Baroja (engineer) was also part of it. The delegated administrator, who was in charge of the actual leadership of the company in Spain, was Arturo Guinner.

Prior to its constitution, the company G. Henfrey & Co. had acquired land in the foothills of the Cabezo del Faro (also known as Cerro de la Farola), in the area known as La Isla, in Puerto de Mazarrón (Anonymous, 1885). In January 1885, the company applied to the city council for the concession of new land in the same area, to build a lead smelter, to be called Santa Elisa (Guillén, 1997). This smelter would be located to the west of the La Esperanza smelter, whose owner unsuccessfully opposed this new land concession.

The factory was inaugurated on August 2, 1886 (Guillén, 1997). When built, it was the most technically advanced smelter in Spain (it even installed electric lighting in 1887), although it did not have a displacement section separating silver from lead. Some 500 workers came to work there, 40 of them destined for the tasks of unloading coal, ferruginous slags (imported from Italy) and minerals, and loading of lead ingots in the port. For transport, it had its own steam ship, called Carolina, which moved between Cartagena and Malaga (Anonymous, 1887).

The Compañía Metalúrgica de Mazarrón, like practically all others established in Spain, initially sent the argentiferous lead it obtained to England for silver separation and lead recovery. The high price charged by

Part of the map drawn in 1875 and 1876 by the Comisión Hidrográfica under the command of Frigate Captain D. José Montojo, by J. Riudavets and Tudury and published by the Dirección de Hidrografía, Madrid, 1877, showing the position of the chimney of the La Esperanza smelter. The lighthouse for navigation is marked in color.

English companies made Deutsche Gold- und Silber-Scheideanstalt formerly Rössler AG decide to do it by itself, for which, in 1887, it built in Hoboken-lez-Anvers, near Antwerp, Belgium, a displacement industry, the Usine des Desargentation, shared in equal parts with the company Frankfurter Metallgesellschaft AG, who also had interests in Spanish mines. In a “financial engineering” operation, Degussa transferred ownership of its shares in the Compañía Metalúrgica de Mazarrón to the Hoboken company, which became its new interim owner. This allowed manipulating the profit and loss accounts of one or the other company through internal sales of metals at prices different from those of the market (Loscertales, 2005).

In 1913 the Hoboken company sold its shares in the Mazarrón Metal Company, valued at 1,393,000 pesetas, to the Frankfurter Metallgesellschaft AG, which also controlled other lead and copper mines in Spain, through the Société Anonyme des Anciens Établissements Sopwith and the Société des Cuivres et Pyrites. The outbreak of the First World War and the corresponding maritime blockades resulted in the “construction lead” being sent to the San Ignacio smelter, located in Santa Lucía, Cartagena. This smelter, built in 1842 by the Franco Española company, had been acquired in 1912 by the Peñarroya Mining and

Obverse and reverse of a medal issued in 1912, commemorating the 25th anniversary of the founding of the Usine des Desargentation de Hoboken, the work of Godefroid. Devreese. Bronze, 7.3 cm in length. Miguel Calvo collection and photo.

Metallurgical Society. In the late 1910s, the Santa Elisa smelter encountered problems due to a lack of personnel in the district, both in the smelter itself and in the mines, so it had to reduce its production, and even went into inactive maintained at times until 1919. In 1924 it managed to process 21,750 tons of ore, but in subsequent years the amount available was less and less, given the decrease in activity of the Cartagena and La Unión mines. The smelter ceased operations at the end of 1927, mainly due to a lack of ore to process. Despite controlling most of the ore produced in Mazarrón, it was insufficient to maintain continuous activity. In the 1960s the smelter was dismantled, to recover the lead that impregnated the bricks of the kiln walls and the galleries that carried the smoke to the chimneys (Belmar, 2011). The smelting facilities were situated in a very favorable location, due to the ease of shipping and the possibility of constructing the general chimney in an elevated position, but there was a lack of space for additional facilities. In order to build the furnaces, large land clearings had to be carried out. One of the most important works needed was the excavation of a trench 60 meters long cutting the hill located NE of the factory for the passage of the railway siding from Mazarrón port (Villasante, 1891). The ore, mostly from this district but with smaller quantities from the El Horcajo and Sierra Alamagrera mines, was first subjected to a roasting process that lasted about 6 hours, in reverberatory furnaces of about 6 tons capacity each. Once calcined, the lead was extracted through Pilsz-type smelting furnaces, 6.4 meters high, with a production capacity of 15 to 17 tons of lead per day. Initially, the factory installed 6 reverberatory furnaces and 2 smelting furnaces, although working only with one of

Founder's bond of the Compañía Metalúrgica de Mazarrón. M. Morales collection.

them and keeping the other in reserve. Consequently, daily production was about 17 tons of lead, with about 50 ounces of silver per ton (Anonymous, 1887). Subsequently, the factory underwent several extensions, greatly increasing its capacity. In the middle of 1888, with three furnaces in operation, it produced about 50 tons of lead per day (Anonymous, 1888). In 1893, the Santa Elisa smelter obtained about 25,000 tons of lead and 33 tons of silver (Oriol, 1895). In 1894 it expanded its facilities again, soon running into the problem that at times it could not get enough ore from the area to keep production at full capacity. For this reason, in 1897, the director requested permission to import argentiferous lead ore from Australia, committing to export the obtained metal (Greif, 1897). In 1926, an electric condensation system was installed at the smoke outlet of the furnaces to recover the metal contained in the dust, although that remained almost unused, since, as already indicated, the supply of ore was scarce at that time. The mixture used for the smelting beds consisted of a quantity of calcined minerals of between 20 and 25 tons and a flux formed by coal, siderite, ferruginous slags, lime, crude ore, and “kills” (the slag material rich in lead that floats on the molten metal and gets recycled), distributed in layers that alternated with layers of coal, up to a total furnace load of about 60-65 tons. Every day about 92 tons of ore were smelted using about 40 tons of coal, coal mix, and coke in equal parts (Villasante, 1891). At various times, the smelter included auriferous quartz from the Rodalquilar (Almería) mines in the processed mixture. The gold remained with the silver in the extraction of this metal,

and up to 8 grams per ingot were recovered in the final separation process (the ingots of the Santa Elisa smelter weighed 50 kg). When the gold content exceeded two grams per ingot, the Mazarrón smelter was paid its value separately from that of silver, with a 15% discount for expenses. Up to 7 kg of gold were obtained from one shipment of ingots in 1902.

A major problem of the smelting process was the removal of the huge quantities of slags produced, about 30 tons a day for each furnace. Not having space inside the factory itself, they had to be deposited along the beach, forming an embankment between the salt flats existing at that time and the sea (Villasante, 1891).

In March 1889, authorization was given to build a wall on the island's beach to gain land from the sea and use it as a slag dump, and in July 1892 it was used for the construction of a Decauville-type railway for transportation. The enormous accumulation of slags gave the place its name, El Gachero.

Keep in mind that these deposits have been removed extensively by the sea, and also by human action. The coastline of Playa del Gachero is currently different from the one existing at the end of the 19th century, so that the emerged surface is much larger, partly precisely because of the slag deposits. The deposits of slags worked in two directions: land was regained from the sea and in addition to this the salt flats were filled in in 1961, and it is probable that a large part of the slags went into the landfill.

Aerial view of the Mazarrón coast, taken from the Zeppelin airship on its trip to South America in 1935. At the far right is the Santa Elisa smelter, and in the background, the salt flats. Cigarette advertising card. Miguel Calvo collection.

Entrance trench to the factory from the NE. In the foreground, the ore calcination furnaces, with a light corrugated sheet roof. In the background you can see the main fireplace, at the Cabezo del Faro. Photograph from 1905. H. Nonnast collection, courtesy of M. C. Guillén.

Mineralogy

The mixture of a large quantity of iron ore and ferruginous slags with galena in the lead extraction process at the Santa Elisa smelter produced very ferruginous slags, as indicated by Villasante (1891). In these slags iron represents around 27.5%, zinc, manganese and sulfur each around 1.5%, lead 0.5% and phosphorous 0.2%. Traces of arsenic, antimony and silver are also present. The slag mass does not consist of true minerals, since they were produced entirely artificially during the smelting process.

They consist mainly of the synthetic equivalents of fayalite and wustite. The slags occasionally also contain metallic lead, especially in the antique slags, and in those deposited in Punta del Rihuete, where traces of elemental copper are present too. Another type of slag from the Santa Elisa smelter has a strongly limonitic appearance, probably the result of another type of metallurgical process.

Minerals formed by geological processes on materials of anthropogenic origin (neof ormation in slags as a product of the action of the atmosphere and especially of sea water) were considered to be “minerals” until a few decades ago, and in fact some new mineral species were described from slags, especially those of Laurion, from the smelters of the classical Greek era and studied since the 19th century (Koechlin, 1887). Since 1995, the possibility that materials produced by new technologies could give rise to an endless number of new substances by exposure to the environment, led the CNMMN (Commission on New Minerals and

Mineral Names) of the International Mineralogical Association to decide not to accept as new minerals the materials produced in this way, although without retroactively demoting those minerals that had been previously approved (Nickel, 1995). Most of the new minerals discovered in slags have subsequently also been found in a completely natural paragenesis. The slags from Puerto de Mazarrón have been in contact with seawater, so the presence of minerals containing chlorine is to be expected. Since slags from Spanish localities have practically not been studied, this is the first time that the presence in Spain of pseudoboleite, paralaurionite, ecdemite, fiedlerite, barstowite, fougérite, ludlockite and nealite are described.

Slag deposits on Playa Gachero, produced by the Santa Elisa smelter in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. Picture W. van den Berg, 2019.

Melting furnaces, with gas outlets and condensation chambers. Photograph from 1905. Col. H. Nonnast, courtesy of M.C. Guillén.

Santa Elisa smelter, with two small heaps of slag used to form slopes. Photographer unknown.

Diaboleite $\text{Pb}_2\text{CuCl}_2(\text{OH})_4$

Copper is quite a rare element in the slags of Puerto de Mazarrón, so copper minerals are not common. Diaboleite has been found occasionally in the Roman slags of Isla Plana and Casas del Caraleño, as prismatic crystals of light sky blue color with a V-shaped base and up to 1.5 mm in length. It appears associated with cumengeite, phosgenite, hydrocerussite, laurionite and paralaurionite. With luck attractive groups of diaboleite crystals in small cavities can be found. In the modern slags of the Santa Elisa smelter it is even rarer, and has only been found as extremely small crystals, of the order of a tenth of a millimeter, associated with phosgenite.

Euhedral crystal of **diaboleite**. Isla Plana. FOV 1.2 mm.

Diaboleite. Euhedral prismatic crystal with multiple acicular grows on the pinacoid. FOV 0.6 mm.

Pseudoboleite $\text{Pb}_{31}\text{Cu}_{24}\text{Cl}_{62}(\text{OH})_{48}$

As previously indicated, copper is a very scarce element in the slags of Puerto de Mazarrón. Pseudoboleite has only been found occasionally but is the most frequent Cu mineral on the slag heaps. It forms nice tabular microcrystals of greenish blue color in the slags of the Casas del Caraleño, often lining cavities completely, more rarely the slags of La Gacha and only in an absolutely exceptional and less distinctive way in the other slag deposits in the area.

Cumengeite $\text{Pb}_{21}\text{Cu}_{20}\text{Cl}_{42}(\text{OH})_{40} \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Cumengeite is a very rare mineral in the slags of Puerto de Mazarrón, and has been found mainly in the oldest, of Roman origin, in the areas of Isla Plana and Casas del Caraleño, as well-formed sparkling deep blue truncated dipyramidal microcrystals up to 0.3 mm, sometimes in attractive combinations with phosgenite crystals. It also appears associated with diaboleite and laurionite. In more modern slags, those from the Santa Elisa smelter, which are generally very poor in copper, it is found only very occasionally, as poorly defined microcrystalline clusters.

Diaboleite. Isla Plana. FOV 0.6 mm.

All specimens in this article are in the collections of Wim van den Berg and Christian Rewitzer. All mineral photos by Christian Rewitzer.

Cumengeite.
Cuboctahedral crystals.
Isla Plana. FOV 0.9 mm.

Cumengeite. Crystals on
phosgenite. Bolnuevo. FOV 2 mm.

Cumengeite. Cuboctahedral blue crystal on a
transparent prismatic phosgenite crystal. Bolnuevo.
FOV 1.4 mm.

Cumengeite. Crystals on phosgenite. Bolnuevo. FOV 0.5 mm.

Laurionite. Tabular prismatic crystals. Isla Plana. FOV 2 mm.

Laurionite. Isla Plana. FOV 1.6 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Laurionite $PbCl(OH)$

Laurionite was discovered as a new mineral species in the old slags of Laurion, in Greece (Koechlin, 1887). In the slags of the Santa Elisa smelter, it is one of the most common lead chlorides, although it is less abundant than penfieldite.

And at La Gacha as well as Casas del Caraleño small but well developed crystals occur also quite frequently. Occasionally the mineral has also been found in the slags at Punta del Rihuete. It appears as microcrystals of generally less than 0.2 mm, although crystals up to 2 mm in length have occasionally been found.

The crystals have the characteristic morphology, tabular development with the pinacoid $\{100\}$ as the dominant figure, elongated in the direction $[010]$, and generally a pointed termination in the shape of a lancet or “Roman sword”, with slightly rounded edges, visible internal growth lines, as in the Laurion specimens (Gelaude *et al.*, 1996). It usually appears associated with nealite, paralaurionite, penfieldite, and phosgenite. Laurionite is difficult to distinguish visually from fiedlerite (which is much rarer in this locality) and from paralaurionite (which is also less frequent). The only usable criteria to distinguish

Laurionite. Isla Plana. FOV 0.8 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Laurionite. Isla Plana. FOV 0.6 mm.
Wim van den Berg coll.

these minerals are the cleavage on the main face of fiedlerite crystals and the presence of twins, which are generally very difficult to distinguish, and also the flexibility of the crystals in the case of paralaurionite. Laurionite had previously been found in Spain in slags from silver extraction altered by sea water in the Cartagena area (Menor, 2010).

Laurionite. Isla Plana. FOV 1.5 mm.
Wim van den Berg coll.

Paralaurionite $PbCl(OH)$

Paralaurionite is less common than laurionite, from which it is very difficult to distinguish, in the Puerto de Mazarrón slags. The mineral occurs at all localities described in this article. Paralaurionite forms sharp, colorless and transparent microcrystals up to 1 mm in size, of tabular morphology, generally twinned and having the typical asymmetrical appearance, as usual for this mineral. Typical for paralaurionite is the often visible flexibility of the crystals.

Laurionite. Isla Plana. FOV 0.8 mm.
Wim van den Berg coll.

Penfieldite $\text{Pb}_2\text{Cl}_3(\text{OH})$

Penfieldite is a mineral that was originally discovered in slag from the Laurion smelters in Greece (Genth, 1892). In fact the vast majority of the localities in which it has been found are deposits of old slags, although it has also been found in some deposits formed without previous human activity, such as the Margarita mine, in Sierra Gorda, Antofagasta, Chile (Szenics, 2003) and the Ferruginosa mine, in Cartagena, Murcia, Spain (Rewitzer *et al.*, 2018).

In the slag vacuoles of the Santa Elisa smelter, penfieldite is very abundant, being the most frequent lead chloride here. It is found as typical striated prismatic crystals with a hexagonal contour, formed by the prism $\{100\}$, terminated by the pinacoid $\{001\}$, with bacillary or acicular development, reaching sizes up to 1 cm, and frequently covering the entire surface. The prism faces have transverse striae, due to the oscillating growth of this figure with a bipyramid, probably $\{11.0.2\}$. Sometimes the crystals are somewhat narrower at the ends, although they very rarely have the fusiform appearance which is common in other locations. It is colorless or has gray tones due to the presence of inclusions.

It is generally associated with barstowite, and less frequently with nealite, laurionite, and the as yet unnamed R42. It is also found in the same form in the Punta del Rihuete slags, with the same associated minerals, although it is scarcer. Smaller but still well formed crystals can be encountered in the slags of Casas del Caraleño and La Gacha.

Penfieldite. Isla Plana. FOV 1.2 mm.
Wim van den Berg coll.

Penfieldite. Isla Plana. FOV 1.8 mm.
Wim van den Berg coll.

Penfieldite. Isla Plana. FOV 2.2 mm.
Wim van den Berg coll.

Ecdemite. Balls formed by aggregates of crystals. FOV 1.4 mm.

Ecdemite $\text{Pb}_6\text{Cl}_4(\text{As}_2\text{O}_7)$

Ecdemite has occasionally been found in the slag vacuoles of the Santa Elisa smelter, as spherules formed by divergently grouped tabular microcrystals, light yellow to white in color. Although the type locality is a natural occurrence, the Langban mine in Sweden, most of the localities where this mineral has been found are slag deposits, such as those of Lauri3n (Greece) and Baratti (Italy).

Fiedlerite $\text{Pb}_3\text{FCl}_4(\text{OH})\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Fiedlerite, along with laurionite, was one of the first minerals whose origin was due to reactions with seawater described from the classical slags of Laurion, Greece (vom Rath, 1887). Since then it has been found in other slags, but its presence

Fiedlerite. Monoclinic parallel crystals. FOV 0.4 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

in deposits of non-anthropogenic origin is uncertain. In slags from the Santa Elisa smelter it is extremely rare compared with laurionite, with which it can be easily confused. It has been found as colorless, transparent or translucent crystals, up to 1.5 mm in size, associated with other lead chlorides. Typical for fiedlerite is a characteristic asymmetrical termination. Despite its scarcity, fiedlerite has been found at all the mentioned localities, with La Gacha producing the nicest specimens. Confusion with laurionite and anglesite is possible, and careful observation is needed to identify fiedlerite crystals.

Barstowite $\text{Pb}_4\text{Cl}_6(\text{CO}_3)\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Barstowite was described as a new mineral species from a specimen found at Bounds Cliff, St. Endellion, Cornwall, a natural outcrop with lead and antimony minerals located in a coastal tidal zone. (Stanley *et al*, 1991). However, it had previously been partially described, although without proposing a name, from specimens found in the oxidation zone of the Kairatky polymetallic deposit in Kazakhstan. All the other deposits mentioned below are at least partly anthropogenic, derived from old smelter slags. Barstowite originates almost always in contact with seawater, as in Lauri3n, Greece (Perchiazzi and Rewitzer, 1995) or from Bruscoline, Capattoli, and Baratti, in Tuscany (Franzini and Perchiazzi, 1992), or, in a special case, as a corrosion product of a lead object recovered from an Etruscan ship sunk 2,100 years ago near present-day Tunisia (Kutzke, 2000). In all these cases, barstowite is a relatively rare mineral.

Barstowite. Acicular crystals. FOV 2.8 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Barstowite. On the left in bacilar crystals. FOV 4.8 mm. C. Rewitzer coll. On the right in acicular crystals. FOV 4.8 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

In slags from the Santa Elisa smelter, in Puerto de Mazarrón, however barstowite is instead relatively frequent and of a very good quality comparable to the best from other localities in the world. It forms groups of colorless or white acicular or capillary crystals with an adamantine luster, individually up to 6 mm in size, sometimes curved, carpeting (or even partially filling in Punta del Rihuete) vugs of up to 2 cm. Even, though they are rare, well terminated crystals can occur. It is very commonly associated with penfieldite, and less frequently with gypsum, phosgenite, laurionite, and nealite. Smaller and less frequent, but still well defined crystals of barstowite have been found at Punta del Rihuete, La Gacha, and Casas del Caraleño.

Cuprite Cu_2O

Despite the limited presence of Cu in the Mazarrón slags, occasionally cuprite can be found. Almost always it forms thin red stainings on elemental Cu, but sometimes minute octahedrons occur.

Litharge PbO

This mineral is above all connected to the cupellation process and is therefore restricted to La Gacha and Casas del Caraleño. It forms small red to brown nodules and is often associated with hydrocerussite, diaboite, and pseudoboite. Archaeological literature mentions that at La Gacha, near the road, large 'litharge cakes' were unearthed during road construction. We found litharge only in limited quantities.

Hydrocalumite $\text{Ca}_4\text{Al}_2(\text{OH})_{12}(\text{Cl}, \text{CO}_3, \text{OH})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Hydrocalumite has been found in the slags of La Gacha, although it is rare. It forms sharp thick monoclinic six-sided crystals up to 1 mm. Instead of the usual transparent to white color, here a red-brown color due to small iron inclusions is notable. There is a close resemblance to the hydrocalumite found in the slags of Laurion.

Fougerite $\text{Fe}^{2+}_4\text{Fe}^{3+}_2(\text{OH})(\text{CO}_3)_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$

Fougerite was characterized as the mineral responsible for a phenomenon known many years ago, but which had no explanation at the molecular level: the color change of some sediments and soils which, when exposed to air, rapidly change from the original blue-green color to the typical ocher of limonitic iron oxides. The reason is the extraordinary instability of this mineral, which oxidizes very quickly in contact with air (Trolard *et al.*, 2007). In soils, the size of the (irregular) fougerite crystals is about 0.5 microns, while in slags it can be up to a thousand times larger, and relatively well formed. They are slightly more stable too because they contain zinc, a cation that partially stabilizes the mineral, but nevertheless are still only preserved as pseudomorphs, transformed into limonite and frequently fragmented during the alteration process.

Ludlockite

Ludlockite was originally discovered in the Tsumeb mine (Embrey *et al.*, 1977), and is considered a very rare mineral present in only a few deposits worldwide. It has also been found in the Greek slags of Laurión (Gelaude *et al.*, 1996), and in the Etruscan slags at various localities in Tuscany (Cerutti and Preite, 1995). Ludlockite is relatively common in the slags from the Santa Elisa smelter, as golden-orange to brown spherules and tufts, up to one millimeter in diameter, but generally much smaller. These aggregates are made up of a divergent association of fusiform spicules, each formed in turn by an association of extremely fine, flexible capillary microcrystals, probably less than one micron in individual thickness. It is commonly associated with vivianite, parasymplectite, and fougérite, and more occasionally nealite and laurionite. In addition to slag from the Santa Elisa smelter, it has also been found in slag from Punta del Rihuete and La Gacha, although in these last two locations it is scarcer.

Ludlockite. Acicular crystals forming divergent spherical aggregates. FOV 0.6 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Ludlockite. FOV 0.6 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Ludlockite. FOV 5 mm. C. Rewitzer coll.

Nealite $\text{Pb}_4\text{Fe}^{2+}(\text{As}^{3+}\text{O}_3)_2\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Nealite is a frequent mineral in slag vugs from the Santa Elisa smelter and also at Punta del Rihuede. It appears as slightly greenish yellow microcrystals in the newly opened cavities, which in a very short time turn orange-yellow, probably due to oxidation of the ferrous iron. Nealite was first found in slags from Laurion, Greece (Dunn and Rouse, 1980), and its existence was definitely confirmed only in several of the slag deposits in that area.

Nealite. FOV 0.8 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Nealite. FOV 4.8 mm. C. Rewitzer coll.

Nealite. Prismatic yellow crystals with orange balls of ludlockite. FOV 0.8 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

The crystals found in the slags of Puerto de Mazarrón have a tabular habit, with the faces corresponding to $\{010\}$ being the more developed, faces that appear striated in a direction parallel to $[001]$. Most have a rectangular outline, formed by the combination of $\{100\}$ and $\{001\}$, those with the combination of $\{100\}$, $\{101\}$ and $\{1\bar{0}1\}$ being much rarer. The crystals, which can exceptionally reach a size of 2 mm, although they generally do not exceed one millimeter, form fan-like clusters or spindles of divergent acicular microcrystals. In some cases, the acicular crystal clusters can fill the vacuoles completely. Nealite appears associated with penfieldite, barstowite, laurionite, and occasionally ludlockite. As already indicated, this is the first time that this mineral has been found in Spain. The abundance and quality of the specimens gives the locality a worldwide significance too.

Nealite. FOV 1.2 mm. C. Rewitzer coll.

Nealite. FOV 1.2 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Nealite. FOV 3.6 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Nealite. FOV 4 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Nealite. FOV 3 mm. C. Rewitzer coll.

Nealite. FOV 3.8 mm. C. Rewitzer coll.

Nealite. FOV 1.8 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Nealite. Triclinic crystals showing the Miller indices.

Nealite. FOV 0.8 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Nealite. FOV 2 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Nealite. FOV 1.9 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

R42. Unnamed mineral. FOV 3.8 mm. C. Rewitzer coll.

R42 $\text{Pb}_5(\text{As}^{3+}\text{O}_3)\text{Cl}_7$

This lead chloroarsenite was first found by one of the authors (CR) in the slags of Laurion, in Greece (Perchiazzi and Rewitzer, 1995), although it could not be described as a new mineral species with its own name, according to IMA criteria, as it was part of materials modified by human action. Its structure was later described by Siidra *et al* (2011). In slag from the “Santa Elisa” smelter it is relatively frequent, in the form of colorless and transparent or milky gray crystals, up to 4 mm in size, with thick tabular development and similar to barite crystals (they belong to the same system and class), formed by the combination of the pinacoid {001}, which is the dominant figure, with the pinacoid {010} and the prism {210}, in addition to other minor figures. It usually appears associated with nealite and penfieldite, and more rarely with phosgenite or barstowite. In the slags of Santa Elisa smelter and at the end in the slags of Punta del Rihuede it has only been found very occasionally.

R42. Unnamed mineral. FOV 4 mm. C. Rewitzer coll.

Phosgenite $\text{Pb}_2\text{CO}_3\text{Cl}_2$
 Phosgenite is relatively common in slags from the Santa Elisa smelter and in Punta del Rihuete, and somewhat less so in El Mojón–La Gacha and Casas del Carraleño. It is found as tabular or prismatic crystals up to 5 mm in size, although they are usually much smaller.

As in other slag deposits, such as Laurion, colorless, transparent and lustrous microcrystals with tabular development are frequent, with the pinacoid {001} as the main figure, or short prismatic and relatively complex morphology, with the pinacoid associated with the tetragonal prisms {010} and {110}, and sometimes with the ditetragonal prism {210}, with poorly developed faces. Faces, usually small but sometimes highly developed, of the tetragonal dipyramid {111} and occasionally of the ditetragonal dipyramid {211} usually appear too. Phosgenite is less common than penfieldite in slag from Puerto de Mazarrón. It appears associated with laurionite, paralaurionite, penfieldite, nealite, and occasionally gypsum.

Tetragonal crystal of **phosgenite** showing the Miller indices of the faces.

Phosgenite. Transparent prismatic crystals with barstowite in divergent aggregates of white acicular crystals. Isla Plana, Mazarrón. FOV 4 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Phosgenite. FOV 2.2 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Phosgenite. FOV 2.5 mm. C. Rewitzer coll.

Phosgenite. FOV 1.4 mm. C. Rewitzer coll.

Aragonite CaCO_3

Aragonite has been found in the limonitic-looking slags of the Santa Elisa smelter, as groupings of colorless transparent, often pointed crystals, up to 2 mm in individual size, and as silky white crusts with a silky luster covering the internal surface of some vacuoles. It seems to be independent of the Pb minerals and often a slag is completely covered with aragonite crystals. The mineral is also found at the other slag deposits of Mazarrón.

Cerussite PbCO_3

Cerussite is found in the slags from all localities examined, although it is not especially common.

Phosgenite. FOV 3.8 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Calcite CaCO_3

Calcite is very rare in the slags of Puerto de Mazarrón, being much less frequent than aragonite. It has occasionally been found in slags of the Santa Elisa smelter and in those of the Casas del Caraleño. Confusion with aragonite is possible and only analysis can tell with certainty.

Cerussite. Twined crystals. FOV 1.4 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Characteristic of this mineral is the variety in forms and twinnings. In the slags of Mazarrón it can be found as whitish needles, prismatic white to transparent crystals with horizontal striations, often showing the typical v-shaped twinning. The maximum size can reach 3 mm.

Hydrocerussite $\text{Pb}_3(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})_2$

Hydrocerussite has been found in slag from the Santa Elisa smelter, as very thin tabular crystals, with the pinacoid {0001} as the dominant figure, and a hexagonal outline formed by small faces of the bipyramid {102}, very small, colorless and transparent. This is the usual morphology in specimens found in other slag deposits, such as those of Laurion (Gelaude *et al.*, 1996). It is also quite common in the slags of Punta del Rihuete and somewhat rarer in those of La Gacha.

Hydrocerussite. FOV 0.2 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Abellaite $\text{NaPb}_2(\text{CO}_3)_2(\text{OH})$

Abellaite is a very rare mineral, discovered in the Eureka mine, Castell-estaó, La Torre de Cabdella, Lleida, Catalonia. In the type locality it is found as extremely small groups of lamellar microcrystals, hexagonal in outline, with the pinacoid as the only distinguishable face, about 30 microns in diameter. In slags from the Santa Elisa smelter it has been very occasionally found as sharp prismatic microcrystals, colorless or white or greenish yellow, up to 300 microns in size, ten times larger than the original locality. This is the first time that this mineral has been found in old slags and, for the moment, those from the Santa Elisa smelter must be considered the best in the world, although abellaite is very rare at this locality.

Anglesita PbSO_4

Anglesite seems to be fairly rare in the slags of Puerto de Mazarrón. It has occasionally been found as transparent colorless or whitish microcrystals, up to 2 mm in size, with the typical diverse morphology of this mineral. It can be found as orthorhombic spear-shaped prismatic crystals, but pseudocubic platy crystals with internal zoning occur too.

Jarosite $\text{KFe}^{3+}_3(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{OH})_6$

Jarosite has been found at the Santa Elisa smelter and at Punta del Rihuede, as small sparkling yellow trigonal crystals forming crusts, identified by EDS analysis. Associated minerals are gypsum and iron-rich minerals.

Plumbojarosite $\text{Pb}_{0.5}\text{Fe}^{3+}_3(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{OH})_6$

This mineral is very rare at Santa Elisa and Punta del Rihuede. And it is almost impossible to distinguish by eye from beudantite, which is more frequent. It forms dark brown minute trigonal crystals in iron-rich slags, associated mainly with gypsum.

Anglesite. Euhedric isolated crystal. FOV 2.4 mm.
Wim van den Berg coll.

Abellaite. Mazarrón. FOV 1 mm.
Wim van den Berg coll.

Jarosite. Cluster of small crystals of octahedral habitus. FOV 0.7 mm. C. Rewitzer coll.

Chenite $\text{Pb}_4\text{Cu}(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{OH})_6$

Chenite appears to be an extremely rare mineral in Puerto de Mazarrón slags, as it has so far been found in only one specimen. It appears, associated with cerussite and hydrocerussite, as light blue prismatic microcrystals, less than a tenth of a millimeter in size.

Caledonite $\text{Pb}_5\text{Cu}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3(\text{CO}_3)(\text{OH})_6$

Like the other copper minerals, caledonite is very rare in slag from Puerto de Mazarrón, and so far has only been found very sparingly, exclusively at Punta del Rihuede and Casas del Caraleño. It appears as light greenish blue prismatic microcrystals, a few tenths of a millimeter long.

Gypsum $\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Gypsum is widely distributed in slags from the Santa Elisa smelter, as sharp colorless or whitish crystals with the usual morphology of this mineral. It is often associated with various lead chlorides. It is also very frequent in the other slag deposits, which presents a problem since it can be confused on initial examination with other interesting species, such as laurionite. The gypsum crystals can reach more than 1 cm in size.

Elyite $\text{Pb}_4\text{Cu}(\text{SO}_4)_2(\text{OH})_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$

Elyite has been found very occasionally only in the slags of Punta del Rihuede, forming the typical violet microcrystals. Elyite seems to be very rare in slags altered by the sea, such as those of Puerto de Mazarrón or those of Laurion. More commonly elyite is found in slags of the old smelters in the Harz mountains, Germany (Van den Berg and Van Loom, 1990).

Caledonite. Blue crystals in a bubble. Bolnuevo. FOV 0.6 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

In Spain, elyite had previously been found only in vugs within the old slags of the abandoned La Cruz smelter, in Linares (Jaén) (Calvo, 2014).

Ettringite $\text{Ca}_6\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3(\text{OH})_{12} \cdot 26\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Ettringite has been found quite frequently in slag from La Gacha, and occasionally in slags from Casas del Caraleño, but not in slag from the Santa Elisa smelter. The mineral forms sharp white needles with a satin luster, grouped in botryoidal aggregates, and also as white hairy aggregates. Especially notable are bright glassy translucent yellow prismatic crystals, and also botryoidal aggregates up to 1 mm, found only at La Gacha.

Beudantite $\text{PbFe}_3(\text{AsO}_4)(\text{SO}_4)(\text{OH})_6$

Beudantite is found especially in the most ferruginous slags of Punta del Rihuede and La Gacha, as tiny crystals of very dark brown or black color, grouped and intergrown to form small continuous layers. With some frequency it is associated with gypsum. This beudantite cannot be differentiated from jarosite or plubojarosite without analysis.

Mimetite $\text{Pb}_5(\text{AsO}_4)_3\text{Cl}$

Mimetite was found in only one Pb-Fe rich slag from the Santa Elisa smelter, associated with ludlockite. It forms yellow and white waxy hexagonal dipyramidal microcrystals with a pointed termination. Vugs up to 2 mm wide can be covered with tiny mimetite crystals up to 0.2 mm size.

Vivianite $\text{Fe}^{2+}_3(\text{PO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Vivianite appears in the slags of the Santa Elisa smelter as small spherules, in which the constituent acicular microcrystals can sometimes be distinguished. It is associated with ludlockite and parasymphesite. In the Punta del Rihuede slags it forms botryoidal aggregates and, occasionally, nice blue platy monoclinic crystals up to 4 mm in size.

Vivianite. Blue tabular crystals. FOV 1 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Mimetite. Divergent aggregates of dipyramidal crystals. FOV 2.5 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Parasymplesite $\text{Fe}^{2+}_3(\text{AsO}_4)_2 \cdot 8\text{H}_2\text{O}$

Parasymplesite is a relatively common secondary mineral in sulfide deposits containing löllingite. It is also found as a product of the alteration of old slags in many localities, although it is usually not abundant. In the slags of the Santa Elisa smelter and at Punta del Rihucete it appears only very occasionally, as bluish green microcrystals grouped together forming botryoidal aggregates. Well terminated greenish monoclinic crystals are very rare. It is associated with vivianite, ludlockite and fougurite (transformed into goethite).

Other minerals

During our investigations of these slag minerals we were also able to identify some previously unknown phases that we would like to mention:

Vivianite. Divergent aggregates of tabular crystals. Alamillo. FOV 2.4 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

MINERALS	Santa Elisa (Playa Gachero)	Alamillo (Punta del Rihuete)	Alamillo (El Mojón -La Gacha)	Bolnuevo (Casas del Caraleño)
Elements				
Native Cu	X	XXX	X	
Native Pb	XXX	XXX	X	X
Sulfides				
Pyrite	XXX	XXX		
Halogenides				
Barstowite	XXX	XX	XX	XX
Cumengeite	X	X	XX	XX
Diaboleite	X	X	XX	XX
Fiedlerite	X	X	X	X
Laurionite	XXX	X	XX	XX
Nealite	XXX	XX		
Paralaurionite	XX	X	XX	XX
Penfieldite	XXX	X	XX	XX
Phosgenite	XXX	XXX	XX	XX
Pseudoboleite	X	X	XX	XXX
Oxides				
Cuprite	X	XX	X	
Fougerite	XXX	XXX		
Hydrocalumite			XX	
Litharge			XX	X
Ludlockite	XX	X	X	
Carbonates				
Abellaite	X			
Aragonite	XX	XX	XX	XX
Calcite	X			X
Cerussite	XX	XX	X	X
Hydrocerussite	XXX	XXX	XX	
Sulfates				
Anglesite	XX	XX	XX	XX
Caledonite		X		X
Chenite	X			
Elyite		X		
Ettringite		X	XXX	XX
Gypsum	XXX	XXX	XXX	XXX
Jarosite	XX	XX		
Plumbojarosite	X	X		
Phosphates				
Beudantite		X	X	
Mimetite	X			
Parasymplesite	XX	X		
Vivianite	XX	XX		
Unknown Minerals (UMO*)				
R42	XXX	X		
CuPbFe Chloride			X	
FeAsO4SO4	X			

* UMO = Mineral Phase only found in slags
x extremely rare/rare
xx fairly frequent
xxx common

Ca Cu Cl phase

Only very few specimens of deep blue spindle-shaped crystals up to 0.3 mm in length could be found in the Mazarron slags. EDS analyses confirm a still unknown mineral, with the chemical composition Ca-Cu-Cl.

Fe AsO₄ SO₄ phase

Beautiful lemon-yellow, tabular crystals and crystal groups were EDS analysed and show the chemical composition Fe-(AsO₄)-(SO₄) that does not match any of the minerals known to date.

Fe-(AsO₄)-(SO₄) phase. FOV 1.8 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Ca-Cu-Cl phase. FOV 0.8 mm. Wim van den Berg coll.

Wim van den Berg

Miguel Calvo

Christian Rewitzer

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